

Deliverable No. 2.6

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	30/09/2019
Submission date:	18/11/2019
File Name:	FarFish D2.6_Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 2_2.0
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final ¹
Dissemination Level:	PU ²

Revision Control

Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix ³
Authors/ Task Leaders	Karim Erzini	CCMAR	22/09/2020	KE
Author	Kim Stobberup	CCMAR	30/09/2019	KS
Reviewer	Arved Staby	IMR	2/10/2019	AS
Reviewer	Karin Olsen	UIT	3/10/2019	KO
Reviewer	Margarita Rincón	CSIC	3/10/2019	MMRH
Reviewer	Mafalda Rangel	CCMAR	10/10/2019	MR
Coordinator	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	22/09/2020	JRV
Administrative Coordinator	Oddur M. Gunnarsson	MATIS	22/09/2020	OMG

¹ Document will be a draft until it was approved by the coordinator

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D2.6

Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 2

22/09/2020

Executive Summary

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast and southwest Atlantic.

Work package 2 within the FarFish project is titled “Advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models” and is, as the title implies, to collect, collate and to some extent analyse biological data relevant for the FarFish case studies. In addition, the work package is to review the current stock assessment models, as well as explore applicability of collecting data via self-sampling by the fishermen.

This document reports on progress in Task 2.3, which is focused at collecting and compiling biological, ecological and fisheries dependent and fisheries independent data that is required for other FarFish work packages. During the first year of FarFish, some modifications in the objectives occurred, resulting in changes in the species which the case studies focus at. For example, in the Cape Verde and Seychelles case studies, the focus is now on by-catch species that are not assessed by the Regional Management Fisheries Organizations (RMFOs) i.e. the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC). Lists of species for each case studies have been drawn up, sources of data identified, contacts have been made with RMFOs and DG MARE, and data compiled. Data compilation has been largely driven by the FarFish Data Base (FFDB) template developed in work package 6 (see deliverables D6.1 and D6.4). On the other hand, other data required for visualization purposes, especially time series, is also being compiled or requested. A formal data request was prepared for DG MARE, while coastal state case study participants were requested to provide data for the FFDB. Data from DG MARE has been received, but not in a readily useable form and therefore required treatment and preparation in order to be of use for FarFish purposes. Talks are also ongoing with RFMOs, especially CECAF, regarding data acquisition and how FarFish can contribute or add value to assessment and management. Acquisition of NANSEN cruise data has proved difficult. Numerous attempts and initiatives have been made, but to date, these have proved largely unsuccessful. Actions that need to be taken by Task 2.3 participants include the provision of data and uploading of data to the FFDB. Task 2.3 is ongoing: D2.8, Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB is due in month 40 (September 2020).

Abbreviations

CA	Convention Area
CCAMLR	Convention for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources
CECAF	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del Mar
CPUE	Catch per unit effort
CS	Case studies
DG Mare	Directorate General of Maritime Affairs
EU	European Union
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FFDB	FarFish DataBase
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
IEO	Instituto Español de Oceanografía
IMROP	The Institut Mauritanien de Recherches Océanographiques et de Peches
INIDEP	Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero (Argentina)
IOTC	Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
ISRA	Institut Senegalais de Recherches Agricoles
MPO	Management Plan Zero (describing current situation)
MR	Management Recommendations
OPROMAR	Organización de Productores de Pesca Fresca del Puerto y Ría de Marín
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisation
SEAFO	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
SFPA	Sustainable fisheries partnership agreements
STECF	(EU) Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Abbreviations	4
1 Introduction	6
2 Overview of data requirements	7
3 Compilation of biological and fisheries data	15
4 Catches of the EU fleet	20
5 Sources of data	27
5.1 Published literature.....	27
5.2 Grey literature	27
5.3 National data bases.....	27
5.4 FAO and Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs)	27
5.5 EAF-Nansen Program	28
6 Conclusions and discussion	29
References	31
Annex 1: Catch by species taken by EU vessels in the context of SFPAs	33
Cape Verde.....	33
Seychelles.....	35
Senegal	36
Mauritania.....	39

1 Introduction

Work package 2 (WP2) within the FarFish project is titled “Advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models” and is, as the title implies, to collect, collate and to some extent analyse biological data relevant for the FarFish case studies. In addition, the work package is to review the current stock assessment models used for fisheries management of the fisheries resources in the case study (CS) countries, as well as explore applicability of collecting data via self-sampling by the fishermen. This document reports on progress within Task 2.3 (Advancing biological and ecological knowledge), biological and ecological data for the relevant stocks in the different CSs have been compiled and made available in the FarFish data base (FFDB) developed in WP6. Considering developments in the context of the project, emphasis has also been placed on compiling catch data and gaining a better understanding of data reporting protocols and procedures. The data collected will feed models and management tools that will provide better understanding of the biology and ecology of the respective species and ecosystems, and will be used by other WPs (1, 3, 4, 5 & 6) for stakeholder interaction, development of management recommendations (MRs), modelling, stock assessment and for visualisation tools.

In this report/deliverable, we provide an overview of the work that has been carried out so far with regards to advancing biological and ecological knowledge in the FarFish project. This work has been driven mainly by the requirements of WP4 & WP6. We also outline the actions that are to be carried out in support of the FarFish during the remainder of the project.

2 Overview of data requirements

One of the objectives of FarFish is to contribute towards advancing knowledge on the current state of stocks by applying data-limited stock assessment methods to species that are not currently assessed. Extensive discussions were held within the project and in consultation with stakeholders (e.g. RFMOs, national authorities, operators, etc.) on identifying suitable candidates (stocks) for this approach. Based on these discussions and reviews carried out (e.g. D2.5 Review of stock assessment methodologies), it became clear that most of the main target species are assessed in an international context, using the best available models, including data-limited methods when this is appropriate. Availability of even basic data on catches makes this problematic in some cases; e.g. very limited fishing activity in the SE Atlantic and fragmented data in the SW Atlantic, due to the lack of a regional fisheries management arrangement.

The focus was thus shifted towards identifying bycatch species as possible candidates for assessment within the context of FarFish. This was to a large extent a response to feedback from RFMOs and CS leaders. A decision was taken to focus on a limited number of key bycatch species from selected CSs, namely Cape Verde and Seychelles, for which there is a particular interest and it is possible to obtain sufficient data to apply the data-limited methods. It is however important to note that the respective RFMOs (ICCAT and IOTC) have struggled in compiling the relevant basic information (catch, effort, sizes, etc.) for most bycatch species. The crucial point here is that the relevant bycatch species are pelagic, oceanic species for which there is no knowledge on stock structure within each ocean basin. Thus, the approach should in principle be to assess on the basis of ocean and not confine this only to the waters of Cape Verde and Seychelles.

An alternative approach was to attempt the assessment of target species, when current efforts have failed to deliver reasonable results. This is the case with sardinellas in the Northwest Africa, where assessments carried out by FAO/CECAF have failed to give reasonable results and for which data-limited methods have not yet been tried (CECAF 2017). This is of particular interest in Mauritania in the context of the SFPA that is in place. However, it is important to consider that the stock areas of sardinellas (*Sardinella aurita* and *S. maderensis*) extend into Senegalese waters.

The following Table 1 presents an update of the relevant species and issues of interest as identified during the first two years of FarFish (D2.3). An overview of the target and by-catch species of interest for each of the CSs, along with sources of information (mainly on catches, assessment etc..) and data gaps.

Table 1: Target and bycatch species considered for data compilation, largely based on the MPO*

SW Atlantic (FAO area 41)		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	Argentine Hake (<i>Merluccius hubbsi</i>) Austral hake (<i>Merluccius australis</i>) Argentine shortfin squid (<i>Illex argentinus</i>) Southern blue whiting (<i>Micromesistius australis</i>).	<p>No management advisory body or Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) exists for International waters of the Patagonian Shelf. There are EU fisheries both in International Waters and in Falkland waters. The available fisheries data appears to be fragmented and not easily accessible (not public). Data holders include Argentinian and Falkland Islands fisheries institutions as well as distant-water fishing nations.</p> <p>Argentine hake is targeted by bottom trawlers from several countries, mostly Spain. International waters are the most important area for Spanish trawlers targeting for hakes in the SW Atlantic. Catches are dominated by Argentine hake and minor catches of Austral hake. The main fishing grounds for <i>M. hubbsi</i> are located between parallels 44°-48°S.</p> <p>Argentine shortfin squid is the most important cephalopod species in the area, and it is the target of major fisheries by both bottom trawlers and jigging vessels during the first half of the year. Bottom trawlers are mainly from Spain, whereas jiggers belong to several Asian countries such as Japan, Korea, Taiwan and China. The main fishing area on the high seas is between parallels 44°-47°S.</p> <p>Southern blue whiting is fished as bycatch in shortfin squid and hake fisheries by bottom trawlers from several countries, mainly from Spain. However, it is a target fishery in Falkland waters.</p> <p>The <i>Instituto Español de Oceanografía</i> (IEO, Spanish Institute of Oceanography) conducted 13 multidisciplinary research cruises in international waters of the SW Atlantic between October 2007 and April 2010 to provide scientific advice for the Spanish Fisheries Administration. The core of this advice, consisting in the proposal of nine candidate areas for closure along the Patagonian Shelf and slope, due to identified presence of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) or sensitive habitats and/or organisms. According to this advice, the Spanish Administration implemented on the 1st July 2011 a fishing ban in the proposed areas for the Spanish bottom trawling fleets operating in the high seas of the SW Atlantic, this ban being still in force.</p> <p>STECF considers that it is unclear if the stocks in international waters constitute separate stocks from those in Argentine or Falkland Islands' waters, so efforts to improve stock identification are desirable.</p>

		<p>STECF notes also that in order to provide informative advice, information from the fisheries exploiting this stock throughout its range is required. STECF also notes the need for a multilateral approach for the assessment and management of the fisheries in the SW Atlantic.</p> <p>Information sources: STECF 2014. Review of scientific advice for 2015. Consolidated Advice on Fish Stocks of Interest to the European Union (STECF-14-24)</p> <p>INIDEP (<i>Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero</i>) (http://www.inidep.edu.ar/), Argentina</p> <p>Falkland Islands Fisheries Dept. (http://www.fig.gov.fk/fisheries/):</p> <p>Wang et al. 2018. A stock assessment for <i>Illex argentinus</i> in Southwest Atlantic using an environmentally dependent surplus production model. <i>Acta Oceanol. Sin.</i>, 2018, Vol. 37, No. 2, P. 94–101; DOI: 10.1007/s13131-017-1131-y</p> <p>Haimovici M, Santos R A D, Bainy M C R S, et al. 2014. Abundance, distribution and population dynamics of the short fin squid <i>Illex argentinus</i> in Southwestern and Southern Brazil. <i>Fisheries Research</i>, 152: 1–12</p> <p>Information gaps/needs: Information on non-EU fleets (e.g. China, Japan, Korea and Taiwan) – important to define how to get the needed information. IEO scientific survey data is not available to the project.</p>
Bycatches	Patagonian grenadier (<i>Macruronus magellanicus</i>) Patagonian toothfish (<i>Dissostichus eleginoides</i>) Rays mantas nei (Raijiformes) Stingrays (<i>Dasyatis</i> spp.) Longtail southern cod (<i>Patagonotothen ramsayi</i>) Forkbeard (<i>Phycis phycis</i>),	<p>The Patagonian toothfish fishery in the Falklands Zone is targeted by a single longline vessel (occasionally two vessels) in waters deeper than 600m and is a non-targeted bycatch species in the trawl fisheries on the shelf. This is managed by the Falkland Islands Fisheries Dept. There is no management advisory body for International waters of the Patagonian Shelf (not covered by CCAMLR).</p> <p>The IEO Spanish surveys also provide information on other demersal and deep-sea resources such as Rockcod (<i>Patagonotothen ramsayi</i>) and Deep-sea grenadiers (<i>Macrourus carinatus</i>, <i>Macrourus holotrachys</i>).</p>

SE Atlantic (FAO area 47)		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	Alfonsino (<i>Beryx splendens</i>) boarfish/pelagic armourhead (<i>Pseudopentaceros richardsoni</i>) Orange roughy (<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>) Deep-sea crab (<i>Chaceon erytheiae</i>) Patagonian toothfish (<i>Dissostichus eleginoides</i>),	<p>These Deep-sea resources are managed by the RFMO established for this purpose (non-tunas): the SE Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO). The SEAFO Convention Area (CA) is a large area with several seamount chains, isolated seamounts, guyots and banks, beyond national jurisdictions. All fishing in SEAFO occurs on or around seamounts. Nowadays vessels have mainly concentrated fishing operations on three distinct areas: Valdivia Bank seamounts complex, Meteor, and Discovery Seamounts. The sum of all TACs amounts to less than 1,000 MT. Fishing appears to have all but ceased.</p> <p>The Commission takes account of scientific advice provided by the Scientific Committee and adopts annual total allowable catch (TACs) for orange roughy (<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>), alfonsino (<i>Beryx splendens</i>), Patagonian toothfish (<i>Dissostichus eleginoides</i>), southern boarfish (<i>Pseudopentaceros richardsoni</i>), and deep-sea red crab (<i>Chaceon erytheiae</i>).</p> <p>SEAFO data is not readily available (www.seafo.org), but the report of the Scientific Committee is downloadable.</p> <p>Important to note that it is CCAMLR who has the responsibility of assessing Patagonian toothfish and recommending a TAC.</p>
Bycatches	Warty dory (<i>Allocyttus verrucosus</i>) Spiky oreo (<i>Neocyttus rhomboidalis</i>) Guinea oreo (<i>Allocyttus guineensis</i>) Smoot oreo dory (<i>Pseudocyttus maculatus</i>), Wreckfish (<i>Polyprion americanus</i>), Grenadiers nei (<i>Macrourus</i> spp.) Blue antimora (<i>Antimora rostrata</i>) King crab (<i>Lithodidae</i> spp., <i>Lithodes ferox</i> , <i>Paralomis formosa</i>) skates, sharks	Data appear to be very limited (e.g. Dr. Fridtjof Nansen and other exploratory surveys). While in 2015 a total of 14 pelagic and bottom trawls were conducted during the Dr. Fridtjof Nansen survey, only video and grab data was collected during the 2019 survey.

Cape Verde		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>), Bigeye tuna (<i>Thunnus obesus</i>), Skipjack tuna (<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>), Swordfish (<i>Xiphias gladius</i>) Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>)	All target stocks are assessed by ICCAT, including Blue shark. Detailed reports on assessment results are available for all these species (www.iccat.int). The models used depend on the quantity and quality of data available (D2.5)
Bycatch	Small tunas group defined by ICCAT: Blackfin tuna (<i>Thunnus atlanticus</i>) Bullet tuna (<i>Auxis rochei</i>) Atlantic bonito (<i>Sarda sarda</i>) Plain bonito (<i>Orcynopsis unicolor</i>) Serra Spanish mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus brasiliensis</i>) Cero (<i>Scomberomorus regalis</i>) Frigate tuna (<i>Auxis thazard</i>) # King mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus cavalla</i>) Little tunny (<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>) West African Spanish mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus tritor</i>) Atlantic Spanish mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus maculatus</i>) Wahoo (<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>) # Dolphinfish (<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>)	The status of small tuna stocks in the ICCAT Convention area is generally unknown. The main issue is that the available fisheries statistics and biological data are generally incomplete and not updated for these species. This places limits on applicable methods/models, including data-limited methods. Information sources: Report of the 2018 ICCAT Small Tuna Species Group Intersessional Meeting (Madrid, Spain 2-6 April 2018) ICCAT databases on nominal catch, catch & effort, size frequency, etc. #Note: Frigate tuna and Wahoo are of particular importance to Cape Verde as they are targets in national fisheries.

Senegal		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	<p>Black hakes: Tropical African hake (<i>Merluccius polli</i>) & Senegalese hake (<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>).</p> <p>*Tropical tunas – PS, LL, PL</p>	<p>Same as below for Black hakes (Mauritania)</p> <p>Tunas assessed by ICCAT (see above Cape Verde)</p> <p>Useful references: Cervantès A., Fall M., White C., Sow F. N., Fernández-Peralta L., Thiam N., Jouffre D. 2017. Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne. Madrid, Espagne, 09 février, 10 et 11 octobre 2017. Rapports des Comités Scientifiques Conjoints. Bruxelles, 60p. + Annexes.</p> <p>Information gaps/needs: Hake species discrimination (the species have overlapping distribution and are mixed in catches and are commonly marketed as <i>Merluccius</i> sp and evaluated as a single stock; lack of knowledge on the two species of hake). Contacts with hake specialists have been made.</p> <p>Note that a self-sampling pilot study has been initiated with the collaboration of OPROMAR, CETMAR and the Universidad de Oviedo. Sampling kits have been prepared by CCMAR and sent to CETMAR for delivery to OPROMAR. The crews of the trawlers will sample hakes for genetic studies that will be carried out by the Universidad de Vigo, with the objectives of: 1) assessing the accuracy of the morphologically based (visual) identification of the two hake species, and 2) the potential use of such sampling to obtain better estimates of catches of the two species.</p>
Bycatches	Varies between 7-15% of trawler catches, consisting mostly of demersal fish, cephalopods and crustaceans	Somewhat similar to the situation in Mauritania

Mauritania		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	<p>Langostino/Prawn (<i>Farfantepenaeus notialis</i>) and Gamba/Southern pink shrimp (<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>).</p> <p>*Black hakes - trawlers *Small pelagics – sardine, sardinella, horse mackerel, mackerel *Atlantic pomfret (<i>Brama brama</i>) - longliners *Tropical tunas – PS, LL, PL</p>	<p>Latest assessments of by FAO/CECAF in 2015 and 2017 (in press), but the data has to be extracted from reports.</p> <p>IMROP is to carry out an assessment of cephalopods (i.e. <i>Octopus vulgaris</i>) in 2018</p> <p>Tunas assessed by ICCAT (see above Cape Verde)</p> <p>Useful reference: Bouzouma M., Corte, A., Daniel, P., 2016. Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne. Nouakchott, Mauritanie, 05 au 07 septembre 2016. Rapports des Comités Scientifiques Conjoints. Bruxelles, 72 p. + Annexes.</p> <p>Information gaps/needs: Stock discrimination (hakes), environmental forcing on small pelagics: Sardine (<i>S. pilchardus</i>), horse mackerels (<i>T. trachurus</i>, <i>T. trecae</i>), mackerel (<i>Scomber colias</i>) and shrimps</p>
Bycatch	<p>Other commercial bycatch species in EU catches:</p> <p>*Shrimp: Alistado (<i>Aristeus varidens</i>), (<i>Penaeus kerathurus</i>), (<i>Aristaeopsis edwardsiana</i>), (<i>Plesionika</i> spp.)</p> <p>*Fish in order of importance: Zeidae, Sparidae, Sharks & Rays, Scorpaeniformes, Lophiidae, Ophidiidae</p>	<p>A few other fish are assessed (Sparidae) by FAO/CECAF</p> <p>Note: there is potential source of conflict with regard access to NANSEN data as the Mauritanian authorities have recently informed FarFish that they too have the intention to explore the use of NANSEN data for stock assessment purposes.</p>

Seychelles		
Category	Species	Available information, data & assessments
Target catches	Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>), Bigeye tuna (<i>Thunnus obesus</i>), Skipjack tuna (<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>). *Swordfish (<i>Xiphias gladius</i>), Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>)	All stocks assessed by IOTC; detailed reports available from relevant working parties (i.e. tropical tuna; www.iotc.org)
Bycatches	Neritic tuna under the management competence of IOTC: Longtail tuna (<i>Thunnus tonggol</i>) Kawakawa (<i>Euthynnus affinis</i>) Frigate tuna (<i>Auxis thazard</i>) Bullet tuna (<i>Auxis rochei</i>) Narrow barred Spanish Mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>) Indo-Pacific king mackerel (<i>Scomberomorus guttatus</i>) Other important bycatch species: Dolphinfish (<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>) Rainbow runner (<i>Elegatis bipinnulata</i>) triggerfish (Balistidae) Wahoo (<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>)	IOTC compiles data for neritic tuna under its management mandate, but stock assessment has been carried out only for three species ((longtail tuna, kawakawa and narrow barred Spanish mackerel). Data is generally incomplete for other species, thus making it difficult to assess even with data-limited methods. The recommendation is to ensure that catches of these non-assessed species do not exceed the average catches estimated between 2009 and 2011. #Note: Dolphinfish and Wahoo are important bycatch species in the Seychelles longline fisheries. Data for other bycatch species are generally lacking or incomplete. Information source: Report of the 8th Session of the IOTC Working Party on Neritic Tunas. Mahé, Seychelles, 21 – 24 August 2017. IOTC–2018–WPNT08–R[E]:73 pp.

*Additional species included after discussions/meetings with CS leaders.

3 Compilation of biological and fisheries data

As previously mentioned, the focus changed towards identifying bycatch species as possible candidates for assessment within the context of FarFish. It is important to point out that the intention is also to combine these efforts with capacity-building initiatives, developing national capacity for analysis and assessment.

A decision was taken to focus on a limited number of key bycatch (or target) species from selected CSs, namely Cape Verde, Seychelles, Senegal and Mauritania, for which it would be possible to obtain sufficient data to apply the data-limited methods. It is however important to bear in mind that the respective RFMOs (ICCAT and IOTC) have struggled in compiling the relevant basic information (catch, effort, sizes, etc.) for most bycatch species.

When considering tuna fisheries, bycatch species are pelagic, oceanic species for which there is no knowledge on stock structure within each ocean basin. Tuna-RFMOs are tasked with compiling data on these bycatch species, including all fleets and areas, but due to their lower commercial importance, data is often deficient and lacking. As there is limited knowledge on stock structure, the common tuna-RFMO approach would be carry out at the regional level. Thus, the approach in FarFish should in principle be to assess on the basis of ocean and not confine this only to the waters of Cape Verde and Seychelles.

In the case of sardinellas in Northwest Africa, assessment was attempted most recently in 2017 by FAO/CECAF but due to data deficiencies it was concluded that the stock assessment model (Length Cohort Analysis) did not yield reasonable results. Thus, it would be interesting to carry out a data-limited modelling approach for comparative purposes.

The selection of species was based on criteria such as:

- Interest to CS country as bycatch (or target) species and/or targeted by national fleets.
- Availability of catch data in the CS country and the respective RFMO (or RFB), including all fleets.
- Availability of CPUE time series, but not necessarily from the CS country.
- Availability of basic life history parameters.
- Not assessed by the respective RFMO or failure to give reasonable results.

The species selected for this exercise were Wahoo (*Acanthocybium solandri*) which is a scombrid fish found worldwide in tropical and subtropical seas. Data was compiled for the Atlantic and Indian Oceans separately (Figure 1 & 2). Wahoo is an important target species of the national fleets in Cape Verde, but it is also a bycatch of tuna fleets.

Figure 1: Catches (tonnes) of Wahoo in the Atlantic Ocean and Cape Verde (CPV). A reasonable CPUE time series (from a directed fishery) was not available. (Source: ICCAT and INDP)

Figure 2: Catches (tonnes) of Wahoo in the Indian Ocean and the Seychelles (SYC) (left-hand) and the available CPUE time series from Reunion Island longline fishery (right-hand). (Source: IOTC)

Another selected species was Frigate tuna (*Auxis thazard*) which is a species of tuna found around the world in tropical oceans. Being a tuna, this species is under the management competence of tuna-RFMOs, but assessment has been limited due to data availability. Data was compiled for the Atlantic Ocean and it should also be noted that this is also target species of national fleets in Cape Verde (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Catches (tonnes) of Frigate tuna in the Atlantic and Cape Verde (CPV) (left-hand) and the available CPUE time series (Series 1: Cape Verde purse seine fishery; Series 2: Spanish purse seine fishery in the Atlantic) (right-hand). (Source: ICCAT)

Common dolphinfish (*Coryphaena hippurus*) was also selected for the Indian Ocean (Figure 4). It is a surface-dwelling fish (non-tuna) found in offshore tropical and subtropical waters, and a common bycatch in tuna fisheries.

Figure 4: Catches (tonnes) of Dolphinfish in the Indian Ocean and the Seychelles (SYC) (left-hand) and the available CPUE time series from Reunion Island longline fishery (right-hand). (Source: IOTC)

In the case of sardinellas in Northwest Africa, assessment was attempted most recently in 2017 by FAO/CECAF but due to data deficiencies it was concluded that the stock assessment model (Length Cohort Analysis) did not yield reasonable results. Thus, it would be interesting to carry out a data-limited modelling approach for comparative purposes (Figure 5 & 6).

Figure 5: Catches of *Sardinella aurita* (tonnes) in Northwest Africa (left-hand) and the available CPUE time series from the Dutch and Russian fleets (right-hand). (Source: FAO/CECAF)

Figure 6: Catch (tonnes) of *Sardinella maderensis* in Northwest Africa and the available CPUE time series from the Dutch fleet. (Source: FAO/CECAF)

Data on some life history parameters was compiled for the selected species to be used for stock assessment using data limited methods (Carruthers and Hordyk, 2017) and uploaded to the FDDB as described in D6.1. The type of data includes: annual catches (landings) or annual indices of relative abundance, catch-at-age data, catch-at-length data, and parameters such as reference points, life history parameters (mortality, growth, length-at-maturity, weight-length), and coefficients of variation (Table 2).

Table 2: Data and parameters being compiled for uploading in the FFDB. * denotes the data that is normally available using various sources.

Catch (landings) and/or indices of abundance
Catch-at-age data
Length-at-age

Parameters & reference points
avg_catch_over_time *
depletion_over_time
M *
FMSY/M
BMSY/B0
MSY
BMSY
length_at_50pc_maturity *
length_at_95pc_maturity
length_at_first_capture *
length_at_full_selection
current_stock_depletion
current_stock_abundance
Von_Bertalanffy_K *
Von_Bertalanffy_Linf *

Von_Bertalanffy_t0 *
Length-weight_parameter_a *
Length-weight_parameter_b *
maximum_age *
reference_overfishing_catch limit

Coefficients of variation of:

catch
depletion_over_time
avg_catch_over_time
abundance_index
M
FMSY/M
BMSY/B0
current_stock_depletion
current_stock_abundance
Von_Bertalanffy_K
Von_Bertalanffy_Linf
Von_Bertalanffy_t0
length_at_50pc_maturity
length_at_first_capture
length_at_full_selection
Length-weight_parameter_a
Length-weight_parameter_b
length_composition

4 Catches of the EU fleet

DG MARE has provided data on catches by EU vessels under the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) and high-seas fisheries fleets. This was a result of a formal request put forward by the coordinator of FarFish, which took into consideration the needs of the various WPs under the project.

The data provided by DG MARE corresponds to the catches taken by EU vessels under SFPAs during the period 2014-2018. These data were provided in pdf format, so considerable effort was needed to transform and make the data readily useable for FarFish purposes. However, it is important to point out that the data was received in mid-2018, so that 2018 data should be considered preliminary and not complete (Table 3). Data on high-seas activity by EU vessels was not provided, but these are available from other databases such as Eurostat and FAO Fishstat, albeit there is at times some uncertainty on catches taken in third country waters or in the high seas.

The data on EU fishery catches under SFPAs consists of 42,856 observations of monthly catches by vessel (Table 3). The data provided for Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and the Seychelles are the most relevant for FarFish, as these correspond to the CSs, but a global overview is available and useful for comparative purposes. The CS countries correspond to about 40% of total observations, which is an indication of the importance of these respective SFPAs in the overall context.

Table 3: Data provided by DGMARE for catches taken in the context of SFPAs. The number of observations included in the data are given, corresponding to monthly aggregated catches by vessel.

Agreement	SFPA Country	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
MAR	Morocco	609	1,758	1,453	1,700	6,30	6,150
CIV	Ivory Coast	101	207	212	131	67	718
COK	Cook Islands				13	7	20
COM	Comoros	24	83	161			268
CPV	Cape Verde	323	422	421	653	411	2,230
GAB	Gabon	260	377	180			817
GNB	Guinea-Bissau		2,824	3,415	3,485		9,724
GRL	Greenland			192	265	174	631
KIR	Kiribati	109	68				177
LBR	Liberia			166	351	121	638
MDG	Madagascar	877	958	1,101	1,013	505	4,454
MOZ	Mozambique	224					224
MRT	Mauritania	2,765	99	2,173	2,349	2,875	10,261
MUS	Mauritius	77	259	165		166	667
SEN	Senegal		357	352	409	198	1,316
STP	São Tome e Principe	227	273	172	196	28	896
SYC	Seychelles	835	647	953	715	515	3,665
Grand Total		6,431	8,332	11,116	11,280	5,697	42,856

Table 4 provides an indication on which EU fleets make most use of the SFPAs concerning CS countries, which is dominated by Spanish vessels in particular and involves different fishing categories. French vessels, as well as Portuguese vessels, are involved in tuna fishing categories primarily. Other EU vessels from northern Europe have a particular interest in the pelagic fisheries off Mauritania (i.e. Germany, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland).

Table 4: Flags of EU vessels making use of the SFPAs in place in the case study countries (Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and the Seychelles). Data given are number of observations.

EU MS	CPV	MRT	SEN	SYC
DEU		93		
DNK				
ESP	2,062	7,902	1,196	1,671
EST				
FRA	108	108	120	1,971
GBR				
GRC		9		
ITA				23
LTU		998		
LVA		509		
NLD		276		
POL		366		
PRT	60			
Grand Total	2,230	10,261	1,316	3,665

The SFPAs with Cape Verde is of particular importance to Spanish tuna fleets, including purse seine, longline and pole-and-line (Amador et al. 2018). The other EU tuna fleets involved, from France and Portugal, account for much lower catches and these appear to be variable (Table 5).

Table 5: Catches (tonnes) of EU vessels taken in the waters of Cape Verde according to fishing category (LLD: drifting longline; LP: Pole and line; SP: Purse seine). 2018 data is provisional.

COUNTRY	FISHING_CAT	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
ESP	CPV_LLD	1,442	2,879	1,944	2,575	1,212	10,052
	CPV_LP	1,228	1,158	896	1,422	2,088	6,792
	CPV_SP	6,052	667	962	6,822	2,826	17,328
ESP Total		8,722	4,703	3,802	10,819	6,126	34,171
FRA	CPV_LP	83	251	517	467	477	1,794
	CPV_SP	1,370			69		1,439
FRA Total		1,453	251	517	536	477	3,234
PRT	CPV_LLD		98	175	118		391
	CPV_LP			0			0
PRT Total			98	175	118		391
Grand Total		10,174	5,052	4,494	11,473	6,603	37,796

The SFPAs with Mauritania consist of a number of fishing categories, including pelagic, demersal and tuna fishing categories (Table 6). Demersal fishing is of particular interest to Spanish fleets (and minor catches taken by Greek vessels). Pelagic fisheries account for most of the catches in volume, including species such as sardine, horse mackerel, sardinellas, and mackerel, most of which are taken by vessels from Germany, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland and the Netherlands. French fleets are interested in tuna fishing categories only (purse seine and pole-and-line).

Table 6: Catches (tonnes) of EU vessels taken in the waters of Mauritania according to fishing category (PEL: Pelagic; CRU: crustaceans; HKM: hakes (fresh); HKM_TMO: hakes (freezer); NTO_DME: other demersal; LLD: drifting longline; LP: Pole and line; SP: Purse seine). 2018 data is provisional.

COUNTRY	FISHING_CAT	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
DEU	MRT_PEL	2,521		10,131	15,304	16,634	44,591
DEU Total		2,521		10,131	15,304	16,634	44,591
ESP	MRT_CRU	1,849	86	937	1,337	1,906	6,115
	MRT_HKM	3,150	246	6,032	6,186	4,317	19,931
	MRT_HKM_TMO				3,392	8,451	11,843
	MRT_LP	2,105		3,280	4,725	1,744	11,853
	MRT_NTO_DME	1,588	63	2,788	2,649	1,407	8,495
	MRT_PEL				97	2,489	2,587
	MRT_SP	8,807		5,559	12,364	11,018	37,748
ESP Total		17,499	395	18,595	30,751	31,332	98,571
FRA	MRT_LP	328		279	285	22	914
	MRT_SP	2,916		1	1,414	400	4,732
FRA Total		3,244		280	1,700	422	5,646
GRC	MRT_CRU				4	16	20
GRC Total					4	16	20
LTU	MRT_PEL	81,822	1,461	45,521	15,126	10,659	154,590
LTU Total		81,822	1,461	45,521	15,126	10,659	154,590
LVA	MRT_PEL	47,052	667	36,680	36,214	29,527	150,140
LVA Total		47,052	667	36,680	36,214	29,527	150,140
NLD	MRT_PEL	108,273		21,327	8,465	12,143	150,209
NLD Total		108,273		21,327	8,465	12,143	150,209
POL	MRT_PEL	19,935		22,308	7,216		49,458
POL Total		19,935		22,308	7,216		49,458
Grand Total		280,347	2,522	154,842	114,780	100,734	653,225

In the case of Senegal, the SFPAs include fishing opportunities in tuna and deep-water demersal trawling. It is primarily Spanish fleets that dominate in all fishing categories, while French vessels are interested in tuna fisheries only (Table 7).

Table 7: Catches (tonnes) of EU vessels taken in the waters of Senegal according to fishing category (DEM_DW: deep-water demersal; LP: Pole and line; SP: Purse seine). 2018 data is provisional.

COUNTRY	FISHING_CAT	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
ESP	SEN_DEM_DW	1,574	206	2,097	74	3,952
	SEN_LP	5,212	5,677	3,024	3,709	17,622
	SEN_SP	772	1,630	2,787	683	5,872
ESP Total		7,558	7,512	7,909	4,467	27,446
FRA	SEN_LP	977	735	522	33	2,267
	SEN_SP	49	237	47	184	518
FRA Total		1,027	973	569	217	2,785
Grand Total		8,584	8,485	8,478	4,683	30,230

The SFPAs with the Seychelles is a tuna-only agreement in the same way as in Cape Verde, but it is of greater importance in terms of catch volumes (Table 8). This SFPAs are of strategic importance to both Spanish and French vessels using purse seine. There is also one Italian purse seiner, but this appears to be a vessel under Spanish management (and beneficial ownership) (Goulding *et al.* 2019)

Table 8: Catches (tonnes) of EU vessels taken in the waters of the Seychelles according to fishing category (SP: Purse seine). 2018 data is provisional

COUNTRY	FISHING_CAT	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
ESP	SYC_SP	21,283	16,791	30,631	23,740	26,681	119,126
ESP Total		21,283	16,791	30,631	23,740	26,681	119,126
FRA	SYC_SP	21,837	15,194	31,173	22,953	13,415	104,573
FRA Total		21,837	15,194	31,173	22,953	13,415	104,573
ITA	SYC_SP			128	1,865	470	2,463
ITA Total				128	1,865	470	2,463
Grand Total		43,120	31,985	61,932	48,558	40,566	226,162

Detailed catch by species is provided in Annex 1, which can be used for identifying bycatch on the basis of specific criteria. Table 9 is a simple compilation of bycatch species in the EU tuna fisheries, carried out in the waters of Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and the Seychelles. It is interesting to see that bycatch species are similar, even though they are taken in various areas and regions. This is for example evident when comparing bycatch species in the purse seine fisheries (category SP), concerning EU vessels fishing in Cape Verde and Seychelles. However, it is interesting to note that pole-and-line fisheries carried out in Mauritanian waters tend to yield more bycatch species such as sharks and billfish (Annex 1).

It is important to note that most of the bycatch species are species under the management competence of the relevant RFMO (ICCAT or IOTC) and may be the target of other fleets and/or other areas.

Table 9: List of common bycatch species in tuna fisheries determined from EU catch data (Cape Verde and Seychelles). LLD: drifting longline; LP: Pole and line; SP: Purse seine. (Source: DG MARE)

Area_Category	FAO_code	Species	English name
Atlantic_LLD	SMA	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Shortfin mako
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna
	LMA	<i>Isurus paucus</i>	Longfin mako
	SSP	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Shortbill spearfish
	BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna
	MLS	<i>Tetrapturus audax</i>	Striped marlin
	SAI	<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Atlantic sailfish
	LEC	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Escolar
	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish
	SPF	<i>Tetrapturus pfluegeri</i>	Longbill spearfish
	WHM	<i>Tetrapturus albidus</i>	Atlantic white marlin
	BUM	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Blue marlin
	Atlantic_LP	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>
ALB		<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore
BLT		<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Bullet tuna
LTA		<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)
BSH		<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Blue shark
SMA		<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Shortfin mako
SWO		<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish
LMA		<i>Isurus paucus</i>	Longfin mako
LEC		<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Escolar
MLS		<i>Tetrapturus audax</i>	Striped marlin
BLM		<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin
SSP		<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Shortbill spearfish
ALB		<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore
SAI		<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Atlantic sailfish
Atlantic_SP	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna
	FRZ	<i>Auxis thazard, A. rochei</i>	Frigate and bullet tunas
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)
	BIL	<i>Istiophoridae</i>	Marlins,sailfishes,etc. nei
Indian Ocean_SP	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore
	TUN	<i>Thunnini</i>	Tunas nei
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna
	BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)
	BIL	<i>Istiophoridae</i>	Marlins,sailfishes,etc. nei
	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish
	WAH	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Wahoo

Table 10 presents a list of bycatch species taken in selected categories of demersal fisheries; hake and crustacean fisheries. A cut-off limit of 10 tons, cumulative over the period 2014-2018, in order to shorten the list of species to be included. This is to illustrate that catches are highly diverse, but it is normally a struggle to obtain data for these species from other fisheries/fleets.

Table 10: List of common bycatch species in selected categories of demersal fisheries determined from EU catch data (Mauritania and Senegal). (Source: DG MARE)

Area_Category	FAO_code	Species	English name	
SEN_DEM_DW	SQE	<i>Todarodes sagittatus</i>	European flying squid	
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory	
	RSE	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Red scorpionfish	
	ANF	<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei	
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)	
	NEC	<i>Pseudophycis bachus</i>	Red codling	
	FOR	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard	
	MRT_CRU	DPS	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	Deep-water rose shrimp
TGS		<i>Penaeus kerathurus</i>	Caramote prawn	
ARV		<i>Aristeus varidens</i>	Striped red shrimp	
PAN		<i>Pandalus spp</i>	Pandalus shrimps nei	
MNZ		<i>Lophius spp</i>	Monkfishes nei	
GER		<i>Chaceon spp</i>	Chaceon geryons nei	
OCZ		<i>Octopus spp</i>	Octopuses nei	
PBA		<i>Penaeus merguensis</i>	Banana prawn	
ARS		<i>Aristaeomorpha foliacea</i>	Giant red shrimp	
PEN		<i>Penaeus spp</i>	Penaeus shrimps nei	
SQC		<i>Loligo spp</i>	Common squids nei	
MON		<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)	
AES		<i>Pandalus montagui</i>	Aesop shrimp	
OCC		<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	Common octopus	
ANK		<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Blackbellied angler	
ANF		<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei	
MRT_HKM		JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory
		JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory
		ANK	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Blackbellied angler
		ANF	<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei
	DEX	<i>Dentex spp</i>	Dentex nei	
	RJC	<i>Raja clavata</i>	Thornback ray	
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora	
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish	
	ORY	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy	
	GUQ	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Leafscale gulper shark	
	GUP	<i>Centrophorus granulosus</i>	Gulper shark	
	BUX	<i>Stromateidae</i>	Butterfishes, pomfrets	
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex	
	POI	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish	
	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel	
	NEC	<i>Pseudophycis bachus</i>	Red codling	
	FOX	<i>Phycis spp</i>	Forkbeards nei	
	WEP	<i>Cynoscion analis</i>	Peruvian weakfish	

Area_Category	FAO_code	Species	English name
	POM	<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>	Florida pompano
	SBR	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	Blackspot(=red)
	XPO	<i>Pampus spp</i>	Silver pomfrets nei
	BSC	<i>Pagrus caeruleostictus</i>	Bluespotted seabream
MRT_HKM_T	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel
	SQE	<i>Todarodes sagittatus</i>	European flying squid
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)
	FOR	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard
	POI	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory
	JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish
	SBG	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Gilthead seabream
	JAI	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	Brown ray
	RSE	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Red scorpionfish
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex
	COB	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i>	Shi drum
	HKN	<i>Merluccius australis</i>	Southern hake

5 Sources of data

5.1 Published literature

For selected species, information on life history parameters, catches, catch-per-unit-effort, stock structure, etc., was compiled from available sources (e.g. primary literature, IOTC and ICCAT papers and reports, Fishbase: www.fishbase.org).

5.2 Grey literature

Grey literature consulted included reports and other publications from national fisheries institutes (e.g. IMROP, INIDEP, ISRA, Falkland Islands Fisheries Department), IEO, RFMOs (ICCAT, IOTC, SEAFO), FAO, reports prepared for the EU (e.g. for DGMARE), and MSc and PhD theses. Some of these sources are referred to in Table 1 and listed in the references. An extensive literature search was carried out using Google Scholar, with key words in English, Spanish, French and Portuguese.

5.3 National data bases

Case study representatives have been requested to provide data from national data bases (national catch statistics, research cruise surveys, selectivity and bycatch and discards studies). In addition to the case study countries, European institutes involved in case study fisheries research, such as the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) have also been contacted. Biological data (size frequency distributions, age frequency distributions, abundance indexes, etc.) was requested from CS leaders for selected species, bycatch species in particular. However, it should be noted that data is in general limited, for bycatch species in particular, and there are sometimes issues of confidentiality which make matters even more complicated.

Other sources of data that have not been provided by the CS partners that are of obvious interest for DLM are the national cruises carried out in the national waters of the CS. For example, time series of fisheries independent catch per unit effort (CPUE) data from research cruises are available from the CS areas and have been used in the past to study trends in abundance (Erzini et al., 2005) and size spectra (Stobberup et al., 2005). Although these data have not been made available, a summary of the pelagic and demersal cruise surveys from CS partners will be provided in the final report.

5.4 FAO and Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs)

The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) and RFMOs such as the ICCAT, IOTC, SEAFO and CEEFAC have been approached as potential sources of data. In fact, the RFMOs compile information and data from the partner countries and carry out stock assessment, with reports and data available online in some cases. RFMOs such as ICCAT and IOTC have been contacted with requests for information (e.g.

Coelho et al. 2017) and to identify how FarFish can contribute, given that in these fisheries, at least for the target species, state of the art stock assessment is already being carried out.

5.5 EAF-Nansen Program

The EAF-Nansen Programme "Strengthening the Knowledge Base for and Implementing an Ecosystem Approach to Marine Fisheries in Developing Countries" is funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs through NORAD. A new EAF-Nansen Programme started in January 2017, carrying forward the objectives of the Nansen Programme, with particular attention to issues of sustainability and threats to marine ecosystems. The Program is a source of data on the status of the marine environment, resource abundance and distribution of living resources. Surveys have been carried out at various times in all the case study countries (Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles). In the SE Atlantic (SEAFO area) a survey was carried out in January – February 2015.

A new cruise with the R/V "Dr Fridtjof Nansen" in the SEAFO area was conducted in January – February 2019 on the Discovery and West seamounts, results of which will be presented at the annual SEAFO Scientific Committee meeting in November 2019, Namibia.

Attempts have been made to gain access to relevant data from the EAF-Nansen Programme from cruises carried out in some of the CS areas, in particular Senegal, but to date there has been limited success, although there is hope that FarFish will be able to obtain data for some of the CSs.

While attempts are being made to obtain the data from cruises that were carried out in the CS areas, the FarFish team has been exploring the Nansen Data Service Repository (http://preface.imr.no/index.php/EAF_Nansen_Data_Service) to identify the cruises that would likely provide useful information for the DLM. Of particular interest are time series of cruises in the same areas. Even if it will not be possible to obtain the data, time series of interest will have been identified and will be included in the final report, allowing scientists from the CS to potentially use this data in the future.

6 Conclusions and discussion

During the second year of FarFish, progress has been made with regard acquisition of data, namely with regard data requested from DG MARE, compilation of time series of catches and CPUE and biological/fisheries parameters for some of the bycatch species selected for study. Nevertheless, there has been limited success in gaining access to other potentially useful sources of data including the EAF-Nansen programme surveys carried out in CS waters, regional fisheries management bodies such as CECAF and national institute survey data, and catch and effort and bycatch of the European Sustainable fisheries partnership agreements (SFPA) fleets.

The major limitation to acquisition of the most relevant and important data for the purposes of FarFish (time series of catch and effort, size distributions) is that these data belong to national institutes and there has been reluctance to provide this data to FarFish. CS partners have declared that they are willing to share data but there should be real collaboration. A possible solution was for the CS partners to bring their data to the DLM courses that had been scheduled to take place. Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 restrictions, these courses have been cancelled or postponed so it has not been possible to access these data.

As the tasks to be carried out under WP2 have changed focus, it is envisaged that CCMAR will be carrying out other tasks that have been specified in various MRs. This concerns a review and assessment of the data being collected through logbooks and the associated protocols and templates in use. This has been specified for Cape Verde where there appears to be some inconsistencies in the data being collected/reported through different channels. A similar review is envisaged for Seychelles and possibly for other CS countries in order to determine the data collection mechanisms in place, as important components of the fisheries information systems.

Despite the shortcomings in terms of acquisition of data, namely Nansen and national research survey time series, we do not think that there will be any significant impact on the ability of the project to deliver expected products or results. The data that has been acquired has been sufficient for demonstration of the DLM package and has been adequate for providing the necessary inputs to the other FarFish WPs. Furthermore, the final report will contain lists and an overview of the time series of data that are available from CS national demersal and pelagic surveys, Nansen surveys as well as other sources. This will serve as an incentive and a basis for the CS partners to apply data-limited approaches for stock assessment of by-catch and other species that are currently not assessed.

There is no need for a contingency plan if no more data becomes available, because the data we have is sufficient to illustrate the utility of the DLM package and we have provided the required data for the other WPs. The objective of FarFish is not to carry out stock assessment for all the species that are not currently assessed by the national research institutes and

RFMOS! Our aim is to provide tools and examples and to identify sources of data that could be used by the tools developed in FarFish. It is up to the CS partners to use the tools with the data that they have, namely time series of fisheries and fisheries independent catch and catch per unit effort data.

References

Amador, T., Cappell, R., Goulding, I. and B. Caillart. 2018. Ex-post and ex-ante evaluation study of the Fisheries Partnership Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Cabo Verde. Prepared by F&S, Poseidon, and Megapesca for DGMARE; 185p.

Bouzouma M., Corte, A., Daniel, P., 2016. Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne. Nouakchott, Mauritanie, 05 au 07 septembre 2016. Rapports des Comités Scientifiques Conjoints. Bruxelles, 72 p. + Annexes.

Carruthers T, Hordyk A. 2017. DLMtool: Data-Limited Methods Toolkit. R package version 5.0.
CCLME 2016. Analyse diagnostique transfrontalière du Grand écosystème marin du courant des Canaries ». CCLME, URC, DAKAR. 144 p.

CECAF/FAO 2018. Report of the FAO Working Group on the Assessment of Small Pelagic Fish off Northwest Africa. Nouadhibou, Mauritania, 22–27 May 2017. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Report No. 1221. Rome.

Cervantès A., Fall M., White C., Sow F. N., Fernández-Peralta L., Thiam N., Jouffre D. 2017. Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne. Madrid, Espagne, 09 février, 10 et 11 octobre 2017. Rapports des Comités Scientifiques Conjoints. Bruxelles, 60p. + Annexes.

Coelho, R., Macías, D., Ortiz Urbina, J., Martins, A., Monteiro, C., Bach, P., Murua, H., Clark, J., Rosa, D., Abaunza, P. 2017. The provision of advice on the conservation of pelagic sharks associated to fishing activity under EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements in the Atlantic Ocean. Final Report. Specific Contract No. 7 under Framework Contract No. MARE/2012/21. 176 pp (including annexes).

CRUISE REPORT "DR. FRIDTJOF NANSEN" EAF – N/2015/2. FAO-NORAD PROJECT NO:
Falkland Islands Fisheries Dept. (<http://www.fig.gov.fk/fisheries/>)
GCP/INT/003/NOR. Investigation of vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs), FISHERIES

Erzini, K., Cheikh A.O. Inejih, and Stobberup, K.A. 2005. An application of two techniques for the analysis of short, multivariate non-stationary time series of Mauritanian trawl survey data. ICES Journal of Marine Science 62: 353-359. 10.1016/j.icesjms.2004.12.009

Goulding, I., Caillart, B. and V. Defaux. 2019. Ex-post and ex-ante evaluation study of the Fisheries Partnership Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Seychelles and of its Implementing Protocol. Prepared by F&S, Poseidon, and Megapesca for DGMARE; 202p.

Haimovici M, Santos R A D, Bainy M C R S, et al. 2014. Abundance, distribution and population dynamics of the short fin squid *Illex argentinus* in Southwestern and Southern Brazil. Fisheries Research, 152: 1–12

ICCAT 2018. Report of the 2018 ICCAT Small Tuna Species Group Intersessional Meeting (Madrid, Spain 2-6 April 2018)

INIDEP (Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero) (<http://www.inidep.edu.ar/>), Argentina

IOTC 2017. Report of the 8th Session of the IOTC Working Party on Neritic Tunas. Mahé, Seychelles, 21 – 24 August 2017. IOTC–2018–WPNT08–R[E]:73 pp.

RESOURCES AND BIODIVERSITY IN THE CONVENTION AREA OF THE SOUTHEAST ATLANTIC FISHERIES ORGANISATION (SEAFO). <http://www.seafo.org/Documents>.

STECF 2014. Review of scientific advice for 2015. Consolidated Advice on Fish Stocks of Interest to the European Union (STECF-14-24)

Stobberup, K.A., Inejih, C.A.O., Traoré, S., Monteiro, C., Amorim, P., and Erzini, K. 2005. Analysis of size spectra in northwest Africa: a useful indicator in tropical areas? ICES Journal of Marine Science 62: 424-429. DOI: 10.1016/j.icesjms.2005.01.014

UE 2017. Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne 2017.

Wang et al. 2018. A stock assessment for *Illex argentinus* in Southwest Atlantic using an environmentally dependent surplus production model. Acta Oceanol. Sin., 2018, Vol. 37, No. 2, P. 94–101; DOI: 10.1007/s13131-017-1131-y

Annex 1: Catch by species taken by EU vessels in the context of SFPAs.

Cape Verde

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
CPV_LLD	BSH	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Blue shark	1327	2726	1888	2400	1041	9383
	SWO	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish	48	111	109	130	58	457
	SMA	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Shortfin mako	51	102	89	124	89	454
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	9	19	16	15	4	63
	LMA	<i>Isurus paucus</i>	Longfin mako		0	2	7	16	25
	SSP	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Shortbill spearfish	5	6	5	4	2	22
	BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin	0	1	4	2	0	8
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna		3	1	3		7
	MLS	<i>Tetrapturus audax</i>	Striped marlin			2	4	0	7
	SAI	<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Atlantic sailfish	1	3	2	1	0	6
	LEC	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Escolar	0	0	0	2	1	4
	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish	0	1	1	0	0	3
	SPF	<i>Tetrapturus pfluegeri</i>	Longbill spearfish		2	1	0		3
	WHM	<i>Tetrapturus albidus</i>	Atlantic white marlin		1				1
	BUM	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Blue marlin	1	0				1
	SFA	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Indo-Pacific sailfish				0		0
	WAH	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Wahoo	0	0		0		0
	BAZ	<i>Sphyaenidae</i>	Barracudas, etc. nei	0			0		0
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore			0			0
CPV_LLD Total				1442	2977	2119	2693	1212	10443

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
CPV_LP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	1288	1222	1009	1358	2401	7278
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	3	88	221	361	128	800
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	21	98	183	170	35	506
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna		1	1	0		2
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore					1	1
CPV_LP Total				1311	1409	1413	1889	2565	8586
CPV_SP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	6634	362	513	5386	2222	15117
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	357	151	271	797	333	1909
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	333	151	171	611	211	1477
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna	96	3	7	89	59	253
	FRZ	<i>Auxis thazard, A. rochei</i>	Frigate and bullet tunas				5		5
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore	2					2
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)				2		2
	BIL	Istiophoridae	Marlins,sailfishes,etc. nei				2		2
	MZZ	Osteichthyes	Marine fishes nei					1	1
CPV_SP Total				7421	667	962	6891	2826	18767
Grand Total				10174	5052	4494	11473	6603	37796

Seychelles

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
SYC_SP	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	23709	17205	30095	24573	12359	107941
	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	15789	12656	28206	19811	24061	100522
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	3567	2075	3452	4054	4136	17282
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore	56	49	96	112	8	321
	TUN	<i>Thunnini</i>	Tunas nei			76			76
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna			3	3	2	8
	BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin			1	2	1	3
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)				3		3
	BIL	<i>Istiophoridae</i>	Marlins,sailfishes,etc. nei			2			2
	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish			1	0	0	2
	WAH	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Wahoo			1	0	0	1
SYC_SP Total				43120	31985	61932	48558	40566	226162
Grand Total				43120	31985	61932	48558	40566	226162

Senegal

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
SEN_DEM_DW	HKM	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	Senegalese hake	1,458	169	1,885	60	3,572
	SQE	<i>Todarodes sagittatus</i>	European flying squid	1	2	122	4	129
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory	43	12	19	4	78
	RSE	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Red scorpionfish		10	28		38
	ANF	<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei	29	0	0	0	30
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)	5		23	0	28
	NEC	<i>Pseudophycis bachus</i>	Red codling	11	1	2	0	14
	FOR	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard		6	4		10
	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel		1	3	4	8
	KPG	<i>Calappa granulata</i>	Shamefaced crab	8				8
	JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory	3	1	1	1	7
	CVJ	<i>Caranx hippos</i>	Crevalle jack	5				5
	SQG	<i>Todarodes angolensis</i>	Angolan flying squid			4	1	4
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora	2	0	1	0	4
	ILL	<i>Illex spp</i>	Shortfin squids nei	2	1			4
	ARV	<i>Aristeus varidens</i>	Striped red shrimp	1		1		3
	RJC	<i>Raja clavata</i>	Thornback ray	2	0		0	2
	ORY	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy	1	0	0	0	2
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish	1	0	0	0	2
	BBS	<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Black scorpionfish	0	0	1		1
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex		1	0		1
	TUN	<i>Thunnini</i>	Tunas nei		0	0		0
	OCC	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	Common octopus	0		0		0
	JAI	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	Brown ray			0		0

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	LOR	<i>Jasus edwardsii</i>	Red rock lobster	0				0
	BSF	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>	Black scabbardfish			0		0
	AJN	<i>Aristeus semidentatus</i>	Smooth red shrimp			0		0
	ARS	<i>Aristaeomorpha foliacea</i>	Giant red shrimp			0		0
	PAR	<i>Pagellus bellottii</i>	Red pandora			0		0
	SDV	<i>Mustelus spp</i>	Smooth-hounds nei	0				0
	EYO	<i>Erythrocles monodi</i>	Atlantic rubyfish			0		0
	TIS	<i>Branchiostegidae</i>	Tilefishes nei			0		0
	SDU	<i>Deania profundorum</i>	Arrowhead dogfish			0		0
	DEP	<i>Dentex gibbosus</i>	Pink dentex			0		0
	MAC	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	Atlantic mackerel			0		0
	XPO	<i>Pampus spp</i>	Silver pomfrets nei			0		0
	GPW	<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i>	White grouper			0		0
	COB	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i>	Shi drum			0		0
SEN_DEM_DW Total				1,574	206	2,097	74	3,952
SEN_LP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	4,856	5,510	3,016	3,484	16,865
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	1,027	539	367	128	2,062
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	157	295	93	65	611
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna	135	53	41		228
	AGC	<i>Amblygaster clupeioides</i>	Bleeker smoothbelly sardinella			16	56	72
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore		3	10	5	18
	AGI	<i>Gymnothorax polygonus</i>	Polygon moray	8				8
	BLT	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Bullet tuna		8			8
	SAA	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	Round sardinella			3	4	7
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)	6				6

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	LIS	<i>Liparis tunicatus</i>	Kelp snailfish		2			2
	RAS	<i>Dussumieria acuta</i>	Rainbow sardine		2			2
SEN_LP Total				6,189	6,412	3,546	3,742	19,889
SEN_SP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	565	1,243	2,424	779	5,011
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	180	475	201	43	899
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	33	55	130	3	221
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna	35	21	69	14	138
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)	8	73	11	28	120
	FRZ	<i>Auxis thazard, A. rochei</i>	Frigate and bullet tunas				1	1
	TUN	<i>Thunnini</i>	Tunas nei		0			0
SEN_SP Total				821	1,867	2,834	867	6,389
Grand Total				8,584	8,485	8,478	4,683	30,230

Mauritania

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
MRT_CRU	DPS	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	Deep-water rose shrimp	780	29	329	547	925	2610
	TGS	<i>Penaeus kerathurus</i>	Caramote prawn	193	43	283	310	87	916
	ARV	<i>Aristeus varidens</i>	Striped red shrimp	335	0	88	132	333	889
	PAN	<i>Pandalus spp</i>	Pandalus shrimps nei	228	2	110	185	205	730
	MNZ	<i>Lophius spp</i>	Monkfishes nei	93	0	43	57	137	331
	GER	<i>Chaceon spp</i>	Chaceon geryons nei	65	0	15	9	92	182
	OCZ	<i>Octopus spp</i>	Octopuses nei	27	2	27	28	54	139
	PBA	<i>Penaeus merguensis</i>	Banana prawn			6	43	26	76
	ARS	<i>Aristaeomorpha foliacea</i>	Giant red shrimp	65					65
	PEN	<i>Penaeus spp</i>	Penaeus shrimps nei	33	10	13			56
	SQC	<i>Loligo spp</i>	Common squids nei	4	0	10	11	3	28
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)				2	16	18
	AES	<i>Pandalus montagui</i>	Aesop shrimp				5	12	17
	OCC	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	Common octopus	1		1	1	8	10
	ANK	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Blackbellied angler	0			0	9	10
	ANF	<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei	6	0	4			10
	ELY	<i>Penaeus longistylus</i>	Red-spot king prawn			0	0	5	6
	SOO	<i>Solea spp</i>		5	0	0		0	5
	SQR	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	European squid			2	0	2	5
	OMZ	<i>Ommastrephidae</i>	Ommastrephidae squids nei	4	0	0			5
	ABS	<i>Penaeus aztecus</i>	Northern brown shrimp			3			3
	GYX	<i>Geryon spp</i>	Geryons nei				0	3	3
	SOP	<i>Penaeus notialis</i>	Southern pink shrimp				3	0	3
	SSH	<i>Plesiopenaeus edwardsianus</i>	Scarlet shrimp	2		0	0	1	3

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	CTC	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	Common cuttlefish	0	0	1	1	1	3
	KPG	<i>Calappa granulata</i>	Shamefaced crab				2	0	2
	SQU	<i>Loliginidae, Ommastrephidae</i>	Various squids nei				2		2
	SBX	<i>Sparidae</i>	Porgies, seabreams nei	2					2
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory	1		0			1
	CET	<i>Dicologlossa cuneata</i>	Wedge sole	0	0	0	0	0	1
	SOX	Soleidae	Soles nei	1	0	0			1
	HLQ	<i>Chlorotocus crassicornis</i>	Green shrimp				0	1	1
	PRB	<i>Penaeus esculentus</i>	Brown tiger prawn	1					1
	GFU	<i>Glyphus marsupialis</i>	Kangaroo shrimp	0					0
	IAX	<i>Sepia spp</i>	Cuttlefishes nei	0	0			0	0
	LKW	<i>Plesionika edwardsii</i>	Striped soldier shrimp	0		0	0	0	0
	CRA	Brachyura	Marine crabs nei					0	0
	SBP	<i>Pagrus spp</i>	Pargo breams nei	0					0
	RRS	<i>Pleoticus robustus</i>	Royal red shrimp				0	0	0
	GPX	<i>Epinephelus spp</i>	Groupers nei			0	0		0
	CPR	<i>Palaemon serratus</i>	Common prawn					0	0
	RXY	<i>Argyrosomus spp</i>	Meagres nei	0					0
	HKX	<i>Merluccius spp</i>	Hakes nei	0			0		0
	MUX	<i>Mullus spp</i>	Surmulletts(=Red mullets) nei	0					0
	OCT	Octopodidae	Octopuses, etc. nei				0		0
	BUX	Stromateidae	Butterfishes, pomfrets nei			0			0
	CRZ	<i>Callinectes danae</i>	Dana swimcrab					0	0
	SQZ	Loliginidae	Inshore squids nei					0	0
MRT_CRU Total				1849	86	937	1342	1922	6136

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
MRT_HKM	HKM	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	Senegalese hake	2795	226	5282	5398	3631	17332
	JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory	22	5	142	156	132	456
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory	52	1	139	149	73	414
	ANK	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Blackbellied angler	167	1	66	56	42	331
	ANF	<i>Lophiidae</i>	Anglerfishes nei		2	50	104	111	268
	DEX	<i>Dentex spp</i>	Dentex nei	13		67	40	37	156
	RJC	<i>Raja clavata</i>	Thornback ray		2	51	53	41	147
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora		4	55	39	33	130
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish	18	1	27	41	21	109
	ORY	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy	21	2	32	21	24	100
	GUQ	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Leafscale gulper shark	6	1	25	7	43	82
	GUP	<i>Centrophorus granulosus</i>	Gulper shark			1	23	37	61
	BUX	Stromateidae	Butterfishes, pomfrets nei	33	0	16		3	52
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex	11	1	13	10	9	44
	POI	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish			10	11	16	37
	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel				11	21	32
	NEC	<i>Pseudophycis bachus</i>	Red codling			1	20	9	30
	FOX	<i>Phycis spp</i>	Forkbeards nei	0		10	3	11	24
	WEP	<i>Cynoscion analis</i>	Peruvian weakfish			9	11	3	24
	POM	<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>	Florida pompano			1	13	6	20
	SBR	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	Blackspot(=red) seabream			5	7	3	15
	XPO	<i>Pampus spp</i>	Silver pomfrets nei			13			13
	BSC	<i>Pagrus caeruleostictus</i>	Bluespotted seabream	2		3	5		10
	SBA	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	Axillary seabream		0	8		0	9
	SRX	Rajiformes	Rays, stingrays, mantas nei	8					8

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	GQD	<i>Plectorhinchus sordidus</i>	Sordid rubberlip			2	5		7
	DEC	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	Common dentex			0	4		4
	DEM	<i>Dentex maroccanus</i>	Morocco dentex			1	2	0	4
	HDV	<i>Schedophilus ovalis</i>	Imperial blackfish					2	2
	GRX	<i>Haemulidae (=Pomadasyidae)</i>	Grunts, sweetlips nei	2					2
	SKH	<i>Selachimorpha (Pleurotremata)</i>	Various sharks nei	0			0	1	2
	DEA	<i>Dentex angolensis</i>	Angolan dentex					1	1
	WRF	<i>Polyprion americanus</i>	Wreckfish			1	1	0	1
	BBS	<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Black scorpionfish			1			1
	TIS	<i>Branchiostegidae</i>	Tilefishes nei					1	1
	PAR	<i>Pagellus bellottii</i>	Red pandora					1	1
	BLB	<i>Stromateus fiatola</i>	Blue butterfish					1	1
	EZS	<i>Scorpaena elongata</i>	Slender rockfish					0	0
	YNV	<i>Cynoscion virescens</i>	Green weakfish	0					0
	UMO	<i>Umbrina ronchus</i>	Fusca drum					0	0
	GBR	<i>Plectorhinchus mediterraneus</i>	Rubberlip grunt			0		0	0
	SKA	<i>Raja spp</i>	Raja rays nei					0	0
	POA	<i>Brama brama</i>	Atlantic pomfret			0		0	0
	BWB	<i>Stromateus stellatus</i>	Starry butterfish			0			0
	REA	<i>Pagrus auriga</i>	Redbanded seabream					0	0
	UAE	<i>Branchiostegus semifasciatus</i>	Zebra tilefish					0	0
	SWA	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	White seabream			0			0
	POX	<i>Trachinotus spp</i>	Pompanos nei					0	0
	GPW	<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i>	White grouper					0	0
	BRY	<i>Brotulina erythrea</i>				0			0

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	TJX	<i>Trachyscorpia cristulata</i>	Atlantic thornyhead					0	0
MRT_HKM Total				3150	246	6032	6186	4317	19931
MRT_HKM_TMO	HKM	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	Senegalese hake				3235	5308	8543
	HKB	<i>Merluccius polli</i>	Benguela hake					2030	2030
	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel				1	281	282
	SQE	<i>Todarodes sagittatus</i>	European flying squid				52	198	250
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)				64	117	181
	FOR	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard				0	167	167
	POI	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish				25	36	61
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory				1	55	56
	JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory				0	47	47
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish				9	28	37
	SBG	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Gilthead seabream				2	29	31
	JAI	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	Brown ray				0	29	30
	RSE	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Red scorpionfish					26	26
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora					22	22
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex				0	16	16
	COB	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i>	Shi drum				0	14	15
	HKN	<i>Merluccius australis</i>	Southern hake					9	9
	ORY	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy				0	7	8
	DEC	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	Common dentex					7	7
	BBS	<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Black scorpionfish				2	2	4
	PAR	<i>Pagellus bellottii</i>	Red pandora					3	3
	DEA	<i>Dentex angolensis</i>	Angolan dentex					3	3
	PAX	<i>Pagellus spp</i>	Pandoras nei					3	3

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	DGS	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	Picked dogfish					3	3
	MAC	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	Atlantic mackerel					1	1
	NEC	<i>Pseudophycis bachus</i>	Red codling					1	1
	CKY	<i>Umbrina canosai</i>	Argentine croaker					1	1
	UAE	<i>Branchiostegus semifasciatus</i>	Zebra tilefish					1	1
	DOI	<i>Dosinia lupinus</i>	Smooth dosinia					1	1
	BLB	<i>Stromateus fiatola</i>	Blue butterfish					1	1
	ALA	<i>Alectis alexandrinus</i>	Alexandria pompano					1	1
	TIS	<i>Branchiostegidae</i>	Tilefishes nei					1	1
	YRS	<i>Sphyraena sphyraena</i>	European barracuda					1	1
	MUT	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	Red mullet					1	1
	LDB	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	Four-spot megrim					0	0
	BSF	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>	Black scabbardfish					0	0
	SYC	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	Small-spotted catshark				0	0	0
	RPG	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	Red porgy					0	0
	BAM	<i>Bathyraja maccaini</i>	McCain's skate					0	0
	SQA	<i>Illex argentinus</i>	Argentine shortfin squid					0	0
	COE	<i>Conger conger</i>	European conger					0	0
	POP	<i>Trachinotus ovatus</i>	Pompano					0	0
	GPW	<i>Epinephelus aeneus</i>	White grouper					0	0
	TMB	<i>Stromateus brasiliensis</i>	Southwest Atlantic butterfish					0	0
	SQD	<i>Solen cylindraceus</i>	Cylindrical razor shell					0	0
	WRF	<i>Polyprion americanus</i>	Wreckfish					0	0
	CGZ	<i>Conger spp</i>	Conger eels nei					0	0
	DEP	<i>Dentex gibbosus</i>	Pink dentex					0	0

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	TOO	<i>Trachinotus maxilloso</i>	Guinean pompano					0	0
MRT_HKM_TMO Total							3392	8451	11843
MRT_LP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	820		2197	3181	1225	7423
	BSH	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Blue shark	175		474	776	197	1622
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	402		299	496	110	1309
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	831		195	112	157	1295
	SMA	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Shortfin mako	197		329	424	66	1016
	SWO	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish	7		30	16	4	57
	LIS	<i>Liparis tunicatus</i>	Kelp snailfish			35			35
	LMA	<i>Isurus paucus</i>	Longfin mako					4	4
	LEC	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Escolar			0	2	0	2
	MLS	<i>Tetrapturus audax</i>	Striped marlin				1		1
	BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin	0		0		0	1
	SSP	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Shortbill spearfish				1		1
	ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore				1		1
	SAI	<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Atlantic sailfish			0			0
	DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Common dolphinfish			0			0
MRT_LP Total				2433		3559	5010	1766	12767
MRT_NTO_DME	POA	<i>Brama brama</i>	Atlantic pomfret	1588	62	2784	2649	1407	8489
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex	0		3			3
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora		1				1
	DEX	<i>Dentex spp</i>	Dentex nei		0	0			0
	BQX	<i>Stromateus spp</i>	Butterfishes nei			0			0
	BUX	<i>Stromateidae</i>	Butterfishes, pomfrets nei		0	0			0
	TCI	<i>Trachinotus africanus</i>	Southern pompano					0	0

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	DEM	<i>Dentex maroccanus</i>	Morocco dentex			0			0
	HDV	<i>Schedophilus ovalis</i>	Imperial blackfish					0	0
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish			0			0
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory			0			0
	WRF	<i>Polyprion americanus</i>	Wreckfish		0				0
MRT_NTO_DME Total				1588	63	2788	2649	1407	8495
MRT_PEL	PIL	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	European pilchard(=Sardine)	90958	87	35356	22678	27852	176931
	HOM	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	Atlantic horse mackerel	14801	1016	62557	33768	22017	134160
	SAA	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	Round sardinella	47188		5342	2435	4771	59736
	MAS	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Pacific chub mackerel	19505	595	11325	5610	3848	40882
	HMZ	<i>Trachurus trecae</i>	Cunene horse mackerel	38073					38073
	MAC	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	Atlantic mackerel	1826	221	9301	11325	8876	31548
	JAX	<i>Trachurus spp</i>	Jack and horse mackerels nei	28653		779	103	35	29570
	SAE	<i>Sardinella maderensis</i>	Madeiran sardinella	10433	45	1740	262	333	12814
	PEL	<i>Osteichthyes</i>	Pelagic fishes nei	2354	51	3991	4751	1515	12663
	LHT	<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i>	Largehead hairtail	452		1879	6		2337
	CUT	<i>Trichiuridae</i>	Hairtails, scabbardfishes nei	1024		841	217	196	2278
	HKE	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	European hake	851	3	656	220	101	1831
	SIX	<i>Sardinella spp</i>	Sardinellas nei	1551	3	175			1729
	BON	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	Atlantic bonito	455	0	528	181	109	1274
	HKM	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	Senegalese hake				82	1051	1133
	LEE	<i>Lichia amia</i>	Leerfish	685	1	27	8	7	727
	POA	<i>Brama brama</i>	Atlantic pomfret	230		206	127	6	570
	BLT	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Bullet tuna	1		383	121	14	519
	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	84	97	175	13	1	370

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	HKB	<i>Merluccius polli</i>	Benguela hake					355	355
	DEC	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	Common dentex	63	7	127	61	33	291
	TUN	Thunnini	Tunas nei			9	213	34	257
	BRU	<i>Brama australis</i>	Southern rays bream	55		131	53		239
	SQE	<i>Todarodes sagittatus</i>	European flying squid				2	144	146
	DEX	<i>Dentex spp</i>	Dentex nei	39		64	22		125
	JOD	<i>Zeus faber</i>	John dory	68		23		15	105
	BLU	<i>Pomatomus saltatrix</i>	Bluefish	82		3	7		92
	MZZ	Osteichthyes	Marine fishes nei	7		82			89
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna			50	28	7	85
	ALF	<i>Beryx spp</i>	Alfonsinos nei	12		30	29	8	80
	SBA	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	Axillary seabream			66			66
	ANE	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	European anchovy			23	27	0	50
	MUL	Mugilidae	Mulletts nei	44				2	46
	GBR	<i>Plectorhinchus mediterraneus</i>	Rubberlip grunt			38			38
	JOS	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i>	Silvery John dory					37	37
	GRA	<i>Parapristipoma octolineatum</i>	African striped grunt	30					30
	BLB	<i>Stromateus fiatola</i>	Blue butterflyfish			0	27	2	30
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)	13			16		29
	FOR	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard					24	24
	FRZ	<i>Auxis thazard, A. rochei</i>	Frigate and bullet tunas	24					24
	VAD	<i>Campogramma glaycos</i>	Vadigo			20	2		21
	MUF	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	Flathead grey mullet	1		9	7	4	21
	PAC	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Common pandora			14	1	5	20
	SCU	<i>Myoxocephalus spp</i>	Sculpins	19					19

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	RSE	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Red scorpionfish					18	18
	MON	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	Angler(=Monk)				6	10	15
	DEL	<i>Dentex macrophthalmus</i>	Large-eye dentex				3	3	6
	SBX	<i>Sparidae</i>	Porgies, seabreams nei	3		3			6
	BRF	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish				3	3	6
	ZEX	<i>Zeidae</i>	Dories nei	6					6
	HKX	<i>Merluccius spp</i>	Hakes nei	3		2			5
	TUX	<i>Scombroidei</i>	Tuna-like fishes nei	4		1			5
	SWA	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	White seabream			5	0		5
	JAI	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	Brown ray				0	4	4
	EYO	<i>Erythrocles monodi</i>	Atlantic rubyfish			3	1		4
	ORY	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	Orange roughy				0	3	3
	COB	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i>	Shi drum					3	3
	BUA	<i>Chloroscombrus chrysurus</i>	Atlantic bumper	2		1			3
	SMC	<i>Arius heudelotii</i>	Smoothmouth sea catfish	0			2		3
	POP	<i>Trachinotus ovatus</i>	Pompano	3					3
	KGM	<i>Scomberomorus cavalla</i>	King mackerel	3					3
	BBS	<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Black scorpionfish				2	0	2
	SBG	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Gilthead seabream				2		2
	DGS	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	Picked dogfish					2	2
	FIN	<i>Osteichthyes</i>	Finfishes nei			2			2
	DEA	<i>Dentex angolensis</i>	Angolan dentex					1	1
	POI	<i>Pontinus kuhlii</i>	Offshore rockfish					1	1
	RYG	<i>Plagiogeneion rubiginosum</i>	Rubyfish				1	0	1
	BAR	<i>Sphyaena spp</i>	Barracudas nei	1					1

FISHING_CAT	FAO_Sp	Species	English name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Grand Total
	TIS	Branchiostegidae	Tilefishes nei					0	0
	HMY	<i>Caranx rhonchus</i>	False scad				0		0
	GAT	<i>Galeichthys feliceps</i>	White barbel	0					0
	YRS	<i>Sphyræna sphyræna</i>	European barracuda					0	0
	BSF	<i>Aphanopus carbo</i>	Black scabbardfish					0	0
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	0					0
	BGR	<i>Pomadasys incisus</i>	Bastard grunt				0		0
	COE	<i>Conger conger</i>	European conger					0	0
	SYC	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	Small-spotted catshark				0		0
	SQD	<i>Solen cylindraceus</i>	Cylindrical razor shell					0	0
MRT_PEL Total				259604	2127	135967	82423	71453	551574
MRT_SP	SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack tuna	10541		4960	11384	10265	37150
	BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna	595		138	929	618	2280
	YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna	525		254	740	154	1673
	FRI	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Frigate tuna	15		208	597	355	1175
	LTA	<i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i>	Little tunny(=Atl.black skipj)				100	8	108
	FRZ	<i>Auxis thazard, A. rochei</i>	Frigate and bullet tunas	32			26	4	61
	BLT	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Bullet tuna	14				14	28
				1			3		4
MRT_SP Total				11724		5560	13779	11418	42480
Grand Total				280347	2522	154842	114780	100734	653225

